

Impact of Buddhism as a Cult in Ancient Kamarupa: A Historical Study

Dr. Kashmiree Gogoi Baruah

Asst. Prof. Department of History, Karmashree Hiteswar Saikia College, Guwahati, Sixmile-22
kashmiree15@gmail.com

Abstract: Buddhism is a philosophy and religion that originated in India in the late 6th century BCE. In 6th century BC some religious movement began to protect society from the domination of priesthood and socio-religious unrest and it was during this time that Buddhism was born in India. Through Buddhism, Gautam Buddha, the founder of Buddhism propagated the message of enlightenment to people. Buddhism has a significant contribution to the Indian culture and civilization. Since very ancient time various religious beliefs existed in ancient Kamarupa and gradually Buddhism made its way in Kamarupa. As Brahmanical religion was to some extent strong in ancient Kamarupa, so Buddhism could not settle in this land easily. Historical evidences tell us about the Brahmanical culture of ancient Kamrupa. But different sources tell us about the development of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa. In this paper an attempt has been made to throw a light on the development of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa and its impact in society.

Keywords: Religion, Beliefs, Development, Buddhism, Culture.

Introduction:

Buddhism played a significant role in the cultural and religious history of India. It is a world religion and it originated in India about 2500 years ago. Buddhism is not merely a religion or philosophy; it is a way of life that provides a key of practice that leads to cheeriness in life. Buddhism gives answers to many problems of human life and true understanding of human mind. Buddhism profoundly influenced the history of India. But Buddhism not only confined to India alone, foreign countries like China, Japan, Thailand, Cambodia, Indonesia, Myanmar, Korea, and Srilanka greatly influenced by the philosophy of Buddhism. The inhabitants of ancient Kamarupa had various folk beliefs and they had practiced all those beliefs as their religion. However, after the influence of Aryan culture, the folk beliefs and religious system of these people had changed. Though Aryan religion (Brahmanical religion) was strong in ancient Kamarupa, but later this region came under the influence of Buddhism too.

Objectives:

The objectives of this paper are to throw a light on the development of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa and the impact of Buddhism in Assamese society.

Methodology:

The method of this paper is descriptive and analytical. Information is collected from secondary sources like books, magazines related to the topic.

Discussion on the theme:

One of the most significant events in the history of India is the birth of Gautam Buddha and the rise of his Buddhism. Like all other world religion, Buddhism also has histories of its development and transformation since its inception. Buddhism gained widespread prominence in the kingdoms of Magadha and Kusala during the reign of king Bimbisara and Prasenjit respectively. As Kamarupa or Pragjyotispur was close to these two kingdoms, the Buddhist influences of these two states touched the land of Kamarupa. However one thing that many would like to say that if Buddhism was influential in ancient Kamarupa then why no Buddha idols of that time found in Assam. But there is a historical truth that there was no idol worship of the Buddha even many years after his death. Because Gautam Buddha never considered himself a God. Therefore there were no idols of Buddha even many years after his death. Initially, the 'Bodhi' tree was worshipped as a symbol of Buddha and that practice was also existed in ancient Kamarupa. In later period, after the introduction of idol worship in Buddhism (Buddhist idol), Buddhist idols were discovered in Assam also. It is known from historical sources that during the reign of Asoka, one Buddhist monk Theravada Dhritika preached the message of Buddhism in Kamarupa¹ Theravada Dhritika was a disciple of Asoka's teacher Upagupta. Therefore, it can be said that Buddhism entered Kamarupa before 226 B.C. During the reign of Asoka Buddhism got the position of state religion in Magadha and it was under the patronage of the royal household that Buddhism influenced other kingdoms. It was during this time that Buddhism probably entered Kamarupa westwards from Nalanda in Bihar and spread throughout the land.

Archaeological evidences and sculpture prove that Vaishnavism spread in the society of Kamarupa from around the 5th century. However, many scholars would like to say that Buddhism did not spread at that time like Vaishnavism. On other hand, the famous Tibetan Historian Taranath describes that long before the arrival of Yuan Chwang, a Buddhist teacher named Dhritik preached Buddhism in Kamarupa and Mahayana Buddhism was preached by a Buddhist scholar named Ashvabhava². Bhaskaravarman who belonged to Varmana dynasty ruled Kamarupa from 600 to 650 AD. It was during this period that the Chinese traveler Yuan Chwang came to Kamarupa. The Chinese traveler Yuan Chwang wrote in his note that Buddhism had almost no influence in Kamarupa during the reign of king Bhaskaravarman³. He also wrote that Buddhists of Kamarupa did not practice Buddhism by showing off. Because they were persecuted if they did so⁴. Bhaskaravarman himself was worshipper of Shiva, but he also believed in Buddhism. Despite his faith in Buddhism and respect for Buddhist teachers, Bhaskaravarman was not willing to discuss Buddhism openly.

Kalhana's Rajatarangini gives information about the prevalence of Buddhism in pre Bhaskaravarman's period. According to Rajatarangini Meghavahana the king of Kashmir married Amritprava, the daughter of Varmana king Balavarmana. This information indicates that Buddhism flourished in Kamarupa even before the reign of Bhaskaravarmana. In addition, the Buddhist people of Tibet, Nepal and Bhutan believe that Gautam Buddha died in Kamarupa⁵. They think the Hayagriva Madhava temple in Hajo as a Buddhist temple and come to worship the idol of Madhava here as belonging to Buddha. Here mention may be made that Amritprabha, the daughter of Kamarupa, built a temple in the name of her father's Buddhist guru Stanpa⁶. The father of Amritprabha is widely believed to be Balavarman, king of the Varman dynasty. It is also known from literary sources that in the ninth century Sankaracharya of south India came to Kamarupa to discuss with the Kamarupa Buddhist scholars about Buddhism. All these prove that Buddhism as a cult had its influence in ancient Kamarupa. Later Buddhism changed its form in Kamarupa and it was known as Tantric Buddhism or Vajrayana, a fusion of monastic philosophy and magic. Vajrayana or Tantric Buddhism is actually a mixture of Mahayana Buddhism and Shakti worship. This Tantric Buddhism gained great popularity in ancient Kamarupa and the Tantra scriptures written in ancient Kamarupa bear witness to this. The Tantra scriptures were widely practiced in this region, hence Kamarupa was known throughout India as the land of magic spells. Some scholars believe that Vajrayana or Tantric Buddhism originated in Bengal and through Bengal it entered in Kamarupa. It is also known that in Kamarupa, Pala king Indrapala was well versed in the Tantras⁷. In fact the kings of Pala dynasty patronized Tantric Buddhism and they were well versed in Tantric scriptures. Therefore it indicates that Tantricism had already been prevalent in Kamarupa. Tantricism as a branch of Mahayana school of Buddhism,

developed about the ninth century under the patronage of Pala kings of Magadha. Vikramasila University which was founded by Pala king Dharmapala became the famous centre of the Tantrik doctrine. From this centre Tantrikism spread into Kamarupa and Tibet⁸.

Vajrayana or mystic Buddhism which also called as “Sahajia cult” found its way into Kamarupa as early as the tenth century. Although part of the original Buddhism, Tantric practices were infused into the Vajrayana branch under the influence of the local Tantric religion of Kamarupa. According to literary sources all the Kamarupi kings including Ratna Pala, followed Tantric Buddhism and from then on Kamarupa became the centre of Vajrayana Buddhism⁹. The inscription (stone tablets) found at Ambari in Guwahati tell us that king Samudrapala of Pala dynasty established a Satra in his capital as a religious center and yogi monks practiced Tantra religion here. Hajo and Kamakhya these two places were the main centre of Tantricism in Kamarupa. The monks, who better known as Siddhas, were mainly responsible for the development of Tantric Buddhism in Kamarupa. In this respect mention may be made of Saraha, Nagarjuna, Savaripa, Luipa, Padmavaira etc and they somehow connected with Kamarupa. It is found that Nagarjuna introduced the original Buddhism in the first century and it was later known as Mahayana Buddhism. This Mahayana form of Buddhism associated a new phase and it developed during the early period of the Guptas. During the period of Pala dynasty, this form of Buddhism gradually developed into Tantricism and it spread to Kamarupa. In Kamarupa, Kamakhya became the centre of this Tantricism.

When Buddhism spread to the plains of Himalaya, there were some small states like Shakya, Malla, Jalla etc. In 5th century the Mallas and the Jallas who were the followers of Buddhism, came to the Goalpara region of ancient Kamarupa. Thus this region of Kamarupa was naturally influenced by Buddhism. Similarly the Bairagi and Kaivarta communities of Assam were formerly followers of Buddhism¹⁰. There are still some evidences of the existence of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa. The Medhghar shrine at Chayagaon in the present Kamrup district was a center of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa. There are many shrines of Buddhism found in present Goalpara district which belonged to the later part of Pala period. Hajo, Nilachal Hill, Singri, Tezpur, Bhaitbari these are some important places of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa. In fact, Gautam Buddha’s easy and simple religion impressed the people of ancient Kamarupa. The influence of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa also influenced the Assamese society. It is found in some literary sources that the Sattra institution of Neo-Vaishnava religion was constructed in the same pattern of the Buddhist shrine. Many Assamese folk literatures reflect the Buddhist thinking. Similarly many folk songs of Assamese society are influenced by the ideas and philosophy of Buddhism like *deh bisarar geet*, *dohas* etc.

Conclusion:

The kings of Kamarupa followed liberal policy in religious field. They were the followers of Brahmanical religion but they followed the policy of toleration in religious field. So their subjects could have followed Brahmanical rituals as well as devotional rituals of Buddhism. Especially tantric Buddhism became influential during the reign of the Pala dynasty and almost all the kings of this dynasty, starting with Ratnapala, were patrons of Tantric beliefs. The archaeological evidences testified the prevalence of Buddhism in Kamarupa. The regions like Suryapahar, Pancharatna in Goalpara, Bhaitbari near Tura in Garopahar give us information about the prevalence of Buddhism in ancient Kamarupa. Literary sources like Taranath’s History of Buddhism gives us information that Buddhism was prevalent ancient Kamarupa.

References:

1. Gogoi, Bonti Rani, Bora, Dibyajyoti, Handique, Sunil, edit, (2014): Buddhism at Work in India, Chandra Prakash, Ghy-1, p-29
2. Barua, Birinchi Kumar, (1969): A Cultural History of Assam, second publication, Guwahati. P-175
3. Hussain, T, P-154
4. Buddhism p-33

5. Nath, Dambarudhar, (2005), Assam Buranji, Arun Prakashan, Guwahati,p.94
6. Ibid, p.94
7. Baruah, Rai K.L.Bahadur,(`2009):Early History of Kamrupa,Bani Mandir, Guwahati, p. 139
8. Ibid, p. 139
9. Gogoi, Bonti Rani, Bora Dibyajyoti, Handique, Sunil, edited, (2014): Buddhism, At Work in India, Culture, History & Philosophy. Chandra Prakash, Guwahati,p.31
10. Ibid, p.31